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Review of Indonesia-Palestine Solidarity Relations: Why is it so Strong?

ABSTRACT

This research discussed reevaluation of the relationship between Indonesia and Palestine. Throughout history in relation of two countries, the relationship has strong solidarity among between the two parties. The author is going to analyze why the solidarity among two nations was very consistent in the long term. In research, the author discovered several important factors: historical, ideological, and humanitarian. This research used qualitative method by references study approach. By reconsideration toward of two states relations, this research pointed new reflection on the relationship between Indonesia and Palestine in the future.

Keyword: The Indonesia-Palestine relation, reconsideration, Indonesia, Palestine

INTRODUCTION

The Israel-Palestinian conflict that occurred in years 2023 made the Palestinian territory, especially Gaza, experience of heavy devastated. The variants of attack which occurred in Gaza resulted damage in food supply, facilities, and humanitarian violations. In any source, noticed that the conflict killed more 3 thousand, severing water access and electricity to 2,3 million people in the Gaza street (Nugraha, 2023). The impact of the conflict attract sympathy to people all over the world as international law violations to Palestinian people brutally.

Indonesia is one of countries that supported Palestine in the conflict not only since years of 2023, but also since Indonesia achieve independence in 1945. During 75 years, Indonesia has been always helping Palestine for free from Israel pressure and achieve their freedom. This assistance effort is done concretely by diplomacy action and support in anything. Indonesia ever provided scholarships to the young Palestinian in University of defense; increased capacity in training;

and the school aids by domestic charitable foundations. Indonesia also provide the health services by building the hospitals such as the hospital of Indonesia in Bayt Lahiya, Gaza, and the hospital in Hebron. Indonesia ever provided the clinic aids such eye clinic and ear, nose, and throat clinic (Nugraha, 2023).

In diplomacy, Indonesia supported Palestine on Israel attacks seriously. The President of Indonesia, Joko Widodo (Jokowi), emphasized the Indonesian support for Palestinian struggle would not subside, either politics or economics. In case of The United States recognition on Jerussalem as capital of Israel in 2017, Jokowi responded that Indonesia condemned the statements. Jokowi also expressed six the important point correlating states proposal on members of Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC). The six points was such as: (1) firm rejection of unilateral recognition; (2) inviting for not following the United States action to move their embassy to Jerussalem; (3) emphasizing the OIC for being activator supporting the Palestinian freedom; (4) demanding the OIC members having diplomatic relations with Israel by reconsider the relations; (5) inviting the OIC members to increase the humanitarian aids and cooperation of economy to Palestine; (6) urging OIC for being activator to support Palestine in many forums suc as international and multilateral (Saragih, 2018). The supporting efforts for Palestine by Indonesia are still consistent. Until years of 2024, Indonesia still condemn Israel and doesn't engage the diplomatic relations as form of support to Palestine and humanitarian.

According to the explanations, the author is doing to know the causes making Indonesia consistently support Palestine in the Israel-Palestine conflicts. Even though this consistency continues to be tested in various conflict cases, Indonesia remains firm in its political stance. By knowing these causes, it is hoped that this evaluation can provide a new reflection on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research methods use qualitative approach. In this context, the author uses qualitative approach as efforts to interpret meaning of Indonesia-Palestine relations. The source which used are books, report, journal, and news. The author analyzed the sources using reflections in historical and political concepts. In searching the sources, the author didn't obtain difficult way. Many sources were obtained in internet and those help the author for finishing the research. Beside the internet, the author used the sources by his private library. In interpreting meaning, the research is full of speculative analysis with reflection of issue. Due to the reflection, the author discussed the topic without left historical narration, then bridging it with the present time. This research tends to scrutinize why the relations among Indonesia and Palestine is very strong. It hopes that the topic can be as reflection among two nations better in the future.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The relations among Indonesia and Palestine was engaged since old. Through 75 years, at least, this relation has been getting stronger each other's. It makes wonderful things that not necessarily exist in other countries. If many nation-states all over the world newly urged to United Nations so that Palestine be free, Indonesia since 1950s had urge the freedom of Palestine. It's not just about genocide's issue in the present. The relations of Indonesia-Palestine more than that. They make solidarity anytime and anywhere.

According to statement, the author is going to analyzed the factors that make relations stronger. Several factors that emerge is about historical reason, ideology, and humanitarian issue. The factors are not single reason, but more complicated. However, these things correspond each other's so that make new meanings. Here is the reasoning of relations both Indonesia and Palestine.

Historical Roots

In historical notes, it shown that Indonesia and Palestine was supported each other's. History revealed that since the transition toward independence until the recognition independence of Indonesia, Palestine became the first nation that spreading the Indonesian freedom. Muhammad Al Husseini, a religion leader, was spreading the information about Indonesian independence through Berlin Radio that have Arabic language. He said congratulations for Islamic world that concur with Japan recognition on Indonesian independence on September 6, 1944. Then, Muhammad Taher, big businessman, sold all of his money in Arabian Bank to support Indonesia' struggle for independence (Harmiyati, 2014).

Palestine was the nations that prominently support Indonesian independence than Egypt, Arab, Afghanistan, and Yemen. Because Palestine as the first nations that triggering other countries to give supported. Indonesia accepted Palestine' support for bless of freedom. Indonesia replied to Palestinian by supporting their freedom from Israeli occupation. The Indonesian government even didn't want to admit for independence recognition of Israel to date. They didn't want to engage of diplomatic relations to Israel.

Since independence of 1945, history revealed that the Indonesian president all of the time had been supporting Palestine, since Soekarno to Jokowi. As example, The Asia Conference 1955 that held in Bandung generate *Dasasila Bandung*. Dasasila Bandung is about the spirit of anti-colonialism and anti-imperialism. This spirit gave enormous energy for freedom. One of the programs was to form Non-Block Movement (GNB) as struggling to Palestine freedom (Muhamad, 2024). the movement declined Israel as a nations-state to join the group because of the Palestine conflict. GNB had strategic position for supporting Palestine. In GNB, Indonesia invite many nations-states that include there to support the freedom of Palestine.

In New Order era, especially when Palestine get freedom but didn't get recognition from United Nations, Indonesia receive the embassy from Palestina. In April 23, 1990, the first ambassador of Palestine gave trust messages to President Soeharto. Then, the government of Iran decided that the main embassy

of Iran in Tunis was accredited to the Palestinian state so that the accreditation of Palestine subordinated on the Jordan Embassy. Unfortunately, the states such as United States, France, and England hadn't recognized of full sovereignty to Palestine (Wati & Burdah, 2024).

In reformation, every president did the same thing. But the anomaly occurred when President Abdurrahman Wahid (Gus Dur) lead Indonesia. After won the election by People's Consultative Assembly (MPR RI), Gus Dur did the different thing about Israel. He would recognize cooperation with Israel, especially in economy. Even though the policy was failed to the decision, this was misunderstanding in his policy because of harming people's heart, specifically moslem. Gus Dur convinced the people that Indonesia should learn to Israel in economy and democracy (Purwono & Najib, 2002). The result of action, one of the policies, made Gus Dur got impeachment by MPR RI. The people accepted the decision because of wrong policy. Then, the next president such as Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono and Jokowi didn't make wrong policy like Gus Dur did.

In general, every president in Indonesia always support Palestine consistently. Outside Gus Dur, they did like Soekarno did in the past. They didn't make history change to worse and didn't make the people heart cracked. Imagined if Soekarno did the mistake of supporting Israel than Palestine, maybe the next president did the same thing, maybe more awful. Through consistent of the founding father, Indonesia obtain good pilot in the future. History pointed a consistency of the leader in Indonesia for supporting Palestina.

Ideological Effect

Either Indonesia or Palestine, they have the same ideology that unite their vision. Islamism is the important factor to understand why Indonesia and Palestine be together. This ideology engaged Indonesia and Palestine, including all of moslem in the rest of the world, and opposed Israel's ideology.

The Palestine territory has significant impact to moslem. It was because there is the Al-Aqsa mosque in Jerussalem, a sacred place of moslem according to Qur'an and hadits. Most moslem believe that they have obliged to protect the

Al-Aqsa. If the land of the Al-Aqsa was occupied, then moslem all of the world must take it back (Xin, 2021). This believe can be a foundation of reasoning for moslem to protect Jerussalem as owned by Palestine.

The ideology of Islam is in contrast with west ideology. West tend to be secularism that separated between religion as private space and socio-political as a public space. Islam didn't separation both of them. The Israel movement which based on Theodore Herzl idea is a secularism that being foundation of Israel (Xin, 2021). Meanwhile, Palestinian keep Islamism as their ideology. This condition makes both the ideology contrast each other's. In reality, history represented the facts that Jerussalem, including the Al-Aqsa mosque, was taken control by Israel since 1967. In 1969, The Al-Aqsa was burned so that get devastated (Muchsin, 2015). This destructive action made most of the moslem in the world condemned Israel.

Indonesia is one of the countries that did for torturing Israel. As the largest of moslem country, Indonesia is more fanatics on supporting Palestine for achieve freedom than Arabian countries tending passive. Islamic ideology can be the important factor. The survey from Psychological Research on Urban Society in Indonesia pointed that the Palestinian conflict was very related with identity as moslem. The similarity of religious identity between Indonesian and Palestinian make significant impact for solidarity as moslem. The survey represent identity of moslem in Indonesia by word indication such as "I am Muslim", "brother in faith" (Shadiqi, Muluk, & Milla, 2020). This similar in faith make the foundation of motivation for solidarity as fellow moslem. It can be basic principles for struggling of the Palestinian freedom.

Beside Islamism, the political ideology of Indonesia also has impact. It can be seemed in the foreign politics of Indonesia, especially in principle policy of free and active (*bebas aktif* in bahasa). This principle has the meaning of anti-colonialism and anti-imperialism that opposed Israel. For Indonesia, colonialism is not in line with justice and humanitarian.

Palestine is just the state in middle east that is going to get their sovereignty and also obtain recognition by United Nations (Prasetya & Srifauzi,

2018). The conflict of Israel-Palestine was open violation of humanitarian to Palestinian. It was historical tragedy. Israel itself has secular ideology from the west and did catastrophic action to Palestine. For every president of Indonesia, it was very contrasting with Indonesian foreign policy and clash with the Indonesian ideology. Yet, it was making sense if Indonesia supported Palestine and condemned Israel.

Humanitarian Issue

The conflict between Israel and Palestine result huge effect for humanitarian issue. In 2023, the conflict give judgement to Israel as genocide practices. It was because the Israel forces targeted civilian, women and children, in Gaza, Palestine. The Gaza city was devastated. At least, according to Human Rights Watch reports, 37,600 people killed. Israel even restricted import of aid to Gaza, as well as medical evacuations (Human Rights Watch, 2024).

In international law, Israel violate the principles of international law, specifically humanitarian issues. Israel potentially violate article 2 (4) and 51 in United Nations Charter as well as violate Geneva Convention 4, protocol 1. This violation is heavy violation that very contrast with humanitarian issue.

The effect of violation was the suffering people of Palestine. By the Israeli forces, this catastrophic moment makes people all over the world angry to Israel. They condemned Israel as genocide crime that oppress the Palestinian people. By the torture, many countries in the world severe diplomatic relations, such as Bahrain, Belize, Bolivia, Chile, Chad, Honduras, Jordan, dan Turkey. These decisions occurred because of human rights abuse of Israel to Palestinian (CNN Indonesia, 2024). Then, the South African movement for urging International Court Justice (ICJ) to Israel leader, Benjamin Netanyahu, for his crime of humanitarian. The people all over the world was doing boycott for companies that affiliate with Israel or supported Israel financially.

Indonesia become the state that opposed Israel violation. Most of Indonesian people was doing boycott the Israel companies and products. The

government of Indonesia supported South Africa for ICJ tribunal and condemned Israel as formal statements. Indonesia invited south countries to stop the war between Israel and Palestine, but not forget to opposed Israel consistently.

The humanitarian issues in present make Indonesian people more loving Palestine. They did sabotage the Israel forces of telecommunication tools by the phone. They feel not doing wrong if they supported Palestine because of humanitarian issues. For making Palestinian survive, Indonesian people delivered humanitarian aid to Gaza. The government of Indonesia help by flying a plane of Hercules C130 J (A-1340) and delivering aid in the air (Kementerian Pertahanan Republik Indonesia, 2024).

CONCLUSION

The relationship between Indonesia and Palestine is a unique relationship. If we imagined, Indonesia and Palestine are very far in geographical area, but they have strong connections like brotherhood that separated in far away. The consistency of Indonesia to pursue the Palestinian freedom resulting vitamins for impunity relationship, though facing any various of test during the history. This relationship makes significant point that there is another factor that make it happened.

The author has three reasoning in analyzing the phenomena. First, the historical factor shown that there is historical consistency of Indonesia for supporting Palestine. Either government or people in Indonesia, they feel of similar suffering with the Palestinian catastrophe by Israel attacks. The leaders of Indonesia, throughout history, has been always consistent in attitude and policy. There is no betrayal for supporting Palestine. All the leader of Indonesia is loyal to Palestine.

Second, the ideological factor pointed that Indonesia and Palestine have similar ideology: Islamism. Though Indonesia is not an Islamic country, but Indonesia is the largest moslem population country in the world. This condition

makes spirit of brotherhood as Islamic ideology. The people of Indonesia, similar with Palestine, believe that The Al-Aqsa mosque is the sacred place that must be protected. Israel is regarded as enemy because they try to destroy the Al-Aqsa. Beside Islamism, the ideology of foreign policy in Indonesia is contrast with Israel ideology. The free and active policy, owned by Indonesia, is the key for opposed Israel violations for humanitarian issues and international law. It because the policy opposed the colonialism of Israel toward Palestinian. This is basic principles that being foundation of Indonesian foreign policy. Yet, Indonesia is always support Palestine for achieve their freedom.

Third, the humanitarian issues provide factor in the present. The brutally attacks of Israel make the relationship Indonesia-Palestine stronger. Because the incident, Indonesia is more confident to support Palestine and feel not doing wrong. Israel got many condemned and loss many things in economy, politic, and images due to violate the international law. One of the pressure group on Israel is Indonesia. This phenomenon make Indonesia is increasingly confident to support Palestine and condemn Israel.

Those three factors are connecting each other's, then influence the Indonesia-Palestine relationship so that keep stronger. Without the factors, the author believes that there is no solidarity for Palestine by Indonesia. If we looked the condition now, we can understand that the solidarity stronger because three factors is still awake and not change otherwise radically. The things happened is those three factors more getting stronger so that the relationship between Indonesia and Palestine is stronger too.

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